

SOLVING THE PROBLEM OF READING CULTURE USING EXAMPLES OF DIFFERENT COUNTRIES

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Annotation: The article examines the problem of reading culture in the information society. Examples of solving this problem in different countries are given. Recommendations are given to help improve the level of reading culture.

Keywords: Reading literacy, reading culture, democratic society, communication, humanity.

The culture of reading is undoubtedly one of the fundamental achievements of humanity as a whole. By the 21st century, we have reached the “peak” of the electrical age, which has led humanity to scientific and technological progress; new forms of obtaining and disseminating information are emerging. Thus, the latest means of communication are popularized. Technical innovations influence established methods of activity.

People’s worldview is changing. A whole generation has already grown up, brought up not in an atmosphere of bookishness, but surrounded by multimedia.” Reading literacy and reading culture have always been highly valued by the world community. In developed countries, literacy is a “reading personality” that has always been considered an invariable value.

The relevance of the problem we are considering is that a reading society is an indisputable condition for a democratic society. Scientists have proven that reading develops memory, improves brain activity, and reduces stress levels in the body. The practical focus of this research: the possibility of using the material during pedagogical councils, when teachers work in schools and other educational institutions and when students prepare abstracts and reports.

In Finland, for example, the Ministry of Culture and Government is involved in solving the reading problem. Reading is actively promoted. A policy was proposed to solve this problem, taking into account each stage of the creation of a book. The measures taken led to excellent results. Funds were allocated for the construction of new libraries, and library services to the population were improved. Residents who are unable to visit libraries now have access to reading.

In Germany, new multimedia tools are used to introduce reading; the Antolin project was created (the project is supported by the Antolin publishing

house). The goal of the project is to create a children's book portal focused on interactive promotion of reading. The essence of the project is for the younger generation to have the opportunity to choose the desired works themselves, followed by questions on the Antolin system for a specific work.

This method develops critical thinking and conscious reading. The child learns to understand the work more deeply. With Antolin, teachers can track the development of their students and thus create a basis for targeted reading support in the classroom.

In France they deal with this problem differently. Reading aloud has become popular on the streets. Volunteers move around the streets and read various works to those who wish. Medical institutions now have shelves with children's books to make waiting for treatment or an appointment in front of the doctor's office more productive. In public places there are special stands depicting excerpts from classic works of literature.

In England, work to popularize reading occurs at a different level. Modern writers are attached to educational institutions and continue their work on creating works, while they actively collaborate with students. Thus, a creative tandem "student-writer" is obtained.

The goal of the work was not to find talented children; the main task was to introduce students to reading and literary creativity. The genres of the works were different - both small-scale poetic works and large-scale works created by a team of students. In order to improve the educational level in schools and other educational institutions, the states of many countries allocate huge sums for the development of libraries. The Ministry of Education ensures that access to information resources is equal for everyone, including criminals, patients, etc.

Promotions are actively held during which children receive books for free. The automation of libraries is also ongoing with a view to their future development. There is the "Confident Start" program, which is aimed at improving the health of the nation and the growth of its educational potential. Schools have a Summer Reading program where children are given summer assignments and students with the highest scores receive prizes.

Reading culture reaches a higher level with the introduction of "Reading Hours" in schools, during which students, together with the teacher, not only get acquainted with the works of classics of Russian and foreign literature, but also analyze them, search for the lexical meanings of unknown words, compose syncwines, and solve crosswords etc. High school students can prepare reports on the works they read or write essays.

In various children's creativity centers and cultural centers, reading circles should be actively organized. In such circles, the younger generation will be able to study the features of literary genres, and children will have the opportunity to learn how to draw up projects and programs.

Such classes will be useful both while studying at school and in higher and secondary educational institutions. The effectiveness of the above activities can only be high if the family, school and library work together. Common efforts can help improve the status of the subject of literature at school and university. Research has proven the effectiveness of reading on a person. A student who reads additional literature has a culture of reading, has analytical thinking, knows how to find ways to solve various problems, and develops harmoniously. Thus, we can conclude that the problem of reading culture occupies an important place not only in our country, but also in other, more developed and developing ones. States are developing programs to improve the level of reading culture of the population. For their successful implementation, cooperation between the school and family and libraries is important. Only through joint efforts can we achieve great goals.

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